
Research

Assessing the Impact of ICT and Its Antecedence on Innovation among Tea Farmers in Rwanda

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Abstract: IT improves agriculture. Rural Rwandan tea producers lack high-tech information. Urban-rural balance is large. ICTs have increasingly been linked to cutting-edge services for data management and number crunching, GIS applications, knowledge-based systems, robots, and better agricultural machinery and processes, as the sector has to innovate and the government promotes off-farm jobs. Linking diverse innovation communities—local, subsectoral, or national—has been neglected. ICTs as "collectors," "analyzers," "sharers," and "disseminators" improve agriculture interventions in poor nations. Affordable smartphone apps help farmers capitalise on marketplaces, adjust to unfavourable agricultural conditions, and communicate with public service agents. Agriculture needs innovation systems. Innovation improves global productivity, competitiveness, and economic growth. Creativity boosts society, wealth, and poverty. Networks, associations, extension services, ICT, and other enablers and bridges can coordinate innovation. ICTs allow researchers, disseminators, users, and network partners to engage and share knowledge. This study employs applicable ideas to identify the main difficulties affecting Rwanda's agricultural tea sector. We evaluated a structural model to identify key factors impacting tea cultivation efficiency and their relationship to promote sustainability. Rwanda's western province's 20–50-year-old farmers, wholesalers, distributors, and exporters take a regular survey. Covariance-based structural equation modelling We study tea farmers' creativity. IT market orientation improves agricultural innovation. 2) ICT and agriculture funding impact innovation. ICT-enhanced agricultural extension boosts innovation to a lesser level. The research links ICT to market orientation, agriculture finance, and innovation. They believe ICT enhanced agricultural innovation. The research proposes Rwandan agricultural tea cultivation business countermeasures based on industrialised nation tea advancements and Rwandan conditions.

Keywords: Rwanda; tea; agricultural innovation

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Introduction and background

In China, tea has been grown and consumed for more than 2,000 years. It is currently the caffeine-containing beverage that is drunk the most globally. Only water is consumed more widely worldwide [1].

Rwanda traditionally produces tea, which is a significant revenue crop. Since being introduced by missionaries in 1952, tea has developed into an industry with a specific exportation goal. The cultivation of tea began on a limited scale and is now developing in the Rwandan Northern, Western, and Southern regions. Due to its favorable temperature, tropical, volcanic soils, and evenly distributed annual rainfall ranging from 1,200 to 1,400 millimeters, Rwanda is naturally favored for growing tea. Most tea is grown in drained marshes and hilly areas between 1,550 m and 2,500 m above sea level [2]. Thousands of household tea producers in rural areas continue to rely heavily on the tea subsector as their main source of income, making it currently Rwanda's largest employer of both casual and self-employed workers [1]. The Rwandan tea industry currently consists of 16 functioning plants that are run by private corporations and 16 cooperatives that bring together a larger number of smallholder tea farmers who control more than 70% of the nation's total tea zones. Over many years, made tea has contributed significantly to the nation's agricultural exports and external revenues.

As one of the best teas in the world, Rwandan tea is renowned for its exceptional quality. Some of the high-quality teas produced in Rwanda include black, orthodox, white, green, organic, and spicy varieties [3]. Rwandan Development Board affirms that Rwandan tea has recently reached an all-time high in value at the monthly East African Tea Trade Association auction in Mombasa. Nearly 70% of the population of working age is still employed in agriculture, which still contributes 24% of Rwanda's national income [4]. Food crops account for almost two thirds of agricultural value. Over the past two decades, agricultural growth has been claimed to have averaged 5.4% annually, with food crop increase accounting for roughly two-thirds of this expansion. Almost 80% of Rwanda's farmers are smallholders who work exclusively or mostly in subsistence agriculture. MINAGRI (the Rwandan Ministry of Agriculture and Animal Resources) and its departments oversee agricultural activity. Aside from that, the NISR (National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda) commissions agricultural surveys and gathers agricultural statistics. Rwanda's 30 districts, which coordinate agricultural activities through district agronomists, cash crop officers, and government-appointed workers in the nation's 416 sectors, are the most significant administrative units of local government [5]. The Crop Intensification Program, which ran from 2007 to 2020, has been Rwanda's primary strategy for promoting agricultural growth over the previous few years.

Every human being's physical and economic survival depends in some manner on agriculture. By 2050, the United Nations projects that there will be more than 9 billion people on the planet [6]. Food output will need to rise by 70% in order to feed everyone. It is difficult to support the world's farmers and fishermen in achieving this goal, but agriculture also plays a vital role in most nations' economies, particularly those in emerging nations. For instance, agriculture contributes one third of the GDP and three quarters of employment in Sub-Saharan Africa, but it also provides employment for 75 percent of the world's poor.

In addition to preventing hunger for very poor households, agricultural development can increase incomes approximately four times more effectively than growth in any other industry. These factors contribute to the explanation of why agricultural development is such an effective strategy for decreasing poverty worldwide and stimulating economic growth. Innovation and innovation systems are essential to and necessary for agricultural progress. In both developed and developing countries, innovation is universally acknowledged as a key driver of increased productivity, competitiveness, and economic growth. Additionally, innovation is crucial for fostering social progress, generating money, and reducing poverty [7]

Effective bridging mechanisms are frequently needed for communication, translation, and mediation across boundaries among the numerous actors in agricultural research and development as well as between knowledge and action in order for innovation to occur. These innovation coordination tools might range from networks, associations, and extension services to ICT as well as other facilitating and bridging systems. By supporting the opening up of the research process to interaction and more accessible knowledge use, ICTs support the opportunity to improve knowledge flows among knowledge producers, disseminators, and users as well as, for example, among network partners. They also support the expansion of stakeholder participation in the innovation and governance process more effectively and at a lower cost [8].

ICTs have more frequently been linked to providing cutting-edge services for data management and number crunching, geospatial applications, knowledge-based systems, and robotics, as well as better farm machinery and processes. However, connecting diverse innovation communities—whether at the local, subsectoral, or national level—has received less attention. Agriculture interventions in poor nations are already being positively impacted by ICTs that act as information "collectors," "analyzers," "sharers," and "disseminators." Access to information on prices, good farming practices, soil fertility, pest or disease outbreaks, and extreme weather has increased farmers' opportunities to capitalize on markets, react to unfavorable agricultural conditions more effectively, and better interact with public service agents thanks in part to affordable mobile applications [8], [9].

Literature review

(1) Information and communication technology in agricultural innovation

The creation of new goods or services can be thought of as innovation [10]. The organizational innovation is the creation of new knowledge and/or alternative delivery techniques. Practice as a new concept, comprising all organizational activities, new goods, new services, or new procedures [11]. The ICT is increasingly viewed as a means of establishing economic linkages and knowledge exchange with the outside world, as well as boosting the transparency and efficiency of reforms and releasing the constraints of existing stakeholders, according to the current conversation on ICT and Rwandan development [12].

Mobile phones are the sole device that the vast majority of low-income country individuals have for connecting to the information society. For instance, Tanzania, a neighbouring country, is one of the least developed nations; Tanzania ranks 160 out of 191 listed nations on the Human Development Index [13], with more than 30% of its 40 million-person population living below the poverty line. The Internet can increase the effectiveness of agricultural markets like cell phones, and it is still the only sector that uses ICT. Developing countries are catching up quickly, though [14].

(2) Market-oriented and innovative

Market orientation is thought of as a way to put the marketing notion into practice and has been identified as a key factor in new product development and company performance [15]. In a vertically coordinated marketing system, market orientation as a unified business philosophy in the supply chain demonstrates that participants in each link of the value chain are focused on serving the needs of the end customer and strategically coordinate with all other chain members to create a superior value proposition.

These studies, on the whole, show a positive association between customer and competitive orientation and the impact on innovation. Market orientation, in particular, increases the ability to innovate through a consumer understanding, enhancing production efficiency, sales, and earnings [16].

According to the study by [17], being customer- and competitor-oriented can improve innovation outcomes. More research revealed that customer and competitor orientation boosted the industry's readiness to produce new goods

and that there is a strong association between customer and competitor orientation and incremental and radical innovation within the industry [11].

(4) Information and communication technology in agricultural extension innovation

When information flows freely, the agri-food industry, like many others, has the potential to become stronger and more sustainable. Many stakeholders are involved in and rely on the local food supply chain, including primary producers, government agencies, food safety authorities, transportation and distribution, consumers, and others. According to research done by [18] Both government and non-governmental organizations have prioritized the development of sustainable local food and agricultural businesses in the Caribbean; improving knowledge mobilization in industry is regarded as a critical aspect in agricultural development and innovation.

A key starting point in efforts to promote a more informed local agri-food system is by improving the quality of agricultural extension and how it is delivered. As a result of promoting the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in rural agriculture, there is the possibility that extension services can be delivered more efficiently and inclusively, thereby contributing to the self-sustaining development of individual agri-food industries. Traditionally the agriculture industry in Rwanda used cooperatives as a way to conduct extension and they are seen as an important institutional vehicle to improve the performance of the smallholder farm sector[19]. Using social media is a great way to reach more consumers, collaborate with colleagues in an effective and timely manner, network within and outside the organization, to share agricultural information, learn from the achievements of other colleagues, and many other things. Promoters are able to do this by using social media tools [20].

ICTs in agricultural financing

Plans for financial sector growth in Africa to address these issues have generated disappointingly few results. Financial intermediaries, relatively high-interest rates, wide intermediation spreads, and significant bank profits continue to exist. Monetary and macroeconomic unpredictability, strong government demand for loan money, a lack of competition, relatively small banks, and contractual concerns, such as limited creditor rights, compromised courts, poor bankruptcy frameworks, and general disregard for contracts, are among the reasons.[21]. Many groups have pioneered novel ways to agricultural funding since the early 2000s. They sometimes employ the notion of microfinance to give agricultural financing, good banking, and mainly agricultural knowledge to enter and flourish in this industry. Many of these new strategies show considerable potential, yet none of them are universally effective. Organizations, on the other hand, can be most effective, innovative, and pragmatic when they are not limited by dogma, use comprehensive risk management methods and technologies, and retain the ability to choose consumers rather than allowing governments to do so.

According to a Chinese study, mobile banking breaks down barriers that have hampered rural lending in China and most of the developing world. When compared to traditional physical networks, it allows financial institutions to provide services to clients more efficiently and provides advantages for gathering, sending, and sharing information. It enables consumers to manage their financial activities despite time, location, and market constraints. Mobile banking has become a significant tool of promoting financial inclusion because it may save time, cut transaction costs, and facilitate financing for a wide range of users. It is an especially promising technology for China's rural financial market, which is still plagued by financial exclusion. [22]

Methodology

This research looks at the impact of ICT on tea producers' inventiveness. To answer the study questions, this work used survey questionnaires to conduct interviews. The empirical data for this study was acquired using a questionnaire distributed to players (producers, self-commercial farmers, dealers, processors, and exporters) at various stages of Rwanda's tea supply chain. These actors were picked for the following reasons: For starters, these

performers have worked in the tea farming industry. That is, they are well-versed in the tea value chain and were willing to discuss it throughout the interview. The invitation to many more actors was turned down. It is vital to have someone who can provide direct knowledge.

Measurement Scales

A thorough examination of the literature on the impact of ICT on tea farmer innovation. Two English instructors assisted in translating the questionnaire into Kinyarwanda and correcting items. As a result, all of the current study's findings were validated in previous researchers' studies. We asked two college association tutors from the School of Economics and Management at Southwest Forestry University to double-check the language and presentation of the defined items in the current study. The pilot survey included 22 items chosen with the assistance of the aforementioned academics. A pilot test was carried out to determine the validity and phrasing of the selected items. All items were scored on a 7-point Likert scale, with "neutral" acting as the mid-point anchor. As indicated by the symbol, items assessing the same variable were obtained. as indicated by [23], grouping items is more acceptable for responders.

Results and discussion

Socio-Demographic information

Below is the list of social-demographic characteristics; the result from 250 participants 37.6% was male, and 62.4% female in terms of age group as indicated in the table below, 2.4% are under 20 years old, 12.8 are between 20 and 30 years, and 35.6% of 250 respondents were age group of 31 up to 40 with an age group of 41 to 50 with 28.0% and remaining 51 and above were 21.2% in terms of education level 50.8% of the largest percentage of respondents have a diploma and 30.4% have below diploma level while 18.8 have a bachelors degree. For the annual income (see Table 1), the largest group whose annual income is between 1 and 5 million with 45.6%, those with less than 1 million are 30.4 % and earners of 5 to 10 million are 18.8 % while the above 10 million are 5.2%.

Table 1 Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	94	37.6	37.6	37.6
	Female	156	62.4	62.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 20	6	2.4	2.4	2.4
	20-30	32	12.8	12.8	15.2
	31-40	89	35.6	35.6	50.8
	41-50	70	28.0	28.0	78.8
	Above 50	53	21.2	21.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below High school	76	30.4	30.4	30.4
	Have High school	127	50.8	50.8	81.2
	Have Bachelors	47	18.8	18.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Annual income

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less Than 1 mill	76	30.4	30.4	30.4
	1-5 million	114	45.6	45.6	76.0
	5-10 million	47	18.8	18.8	94.8
	More than 10 million	13	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Latent variables and their indicator

ICT and process innovation

1. New or significantly improved logistics, delivery or distribution methods of the inputs
2. Entered new markets or increased market share
3. we were able to adapt to weather changes thanks to meteo services available on our phones
4. Reduced time to respond to customer or supplier needs
5. the process of growing Tea is maintained and improved when communication is efficient

ICT and Market orientation

6. New or significantly improved knowledge management systems to better use or exchange information, knowledge and skills within your enterprise
7. Significant changes to the design or packaging of a good or service (Exclude routine/ seasonal changes such as clothing fashions)
8. New or significantly changed sales or distribution methods, such as the internet sales, franchising, direct sales or distribution licenses.
9. Reduced time to respond to customer or supplier needs
10. Reduced costs per unit output

ICT and Agriculture extension

- 11. I feel that agriculture-based information cannot be provided on agriculture-based/Facebook
- 12. I feel it would be difficult for me to share farm-based information through WhatsApp/Facebook with others
- 13. F.M Radio programs provide us with critical work-related information
- 14. I receive mobile SMS from the facilitators on how to improve productivity which is helpful for work-related

ICT and Agriculture financing

- 15. Mobile money helps in saving money
- 16. I use my mobile money account to apply for a loan
- 17. I believe mobile money can be a substitute for formal banking
- 18. we can recommend to other farmers to use mobile money

ICT

- 19. I use my mobile phone daily
- 20. Internet is so useful in tea farming
- 21. ICT is very crucial to making our farming efficient and profitable

Normality Check

In this study, the CFA and SEM will be determined using the Maximum Likelihood estimation method. First, we tested if the data nearly follow a normal distribution. In general terms, complete standards of kurtosis indexes greater than 10 fundamental values of skew indexes larger than 3 indicate a direct violation of normality [24]. In this paper, the skewness indexes scale from -1.824 to 0.234, and the kurtosis indexes range from 1.625 to 5.735. As a result, we can show Table 2 that there is no violation of normality.

Table 2 Assessment of normality (Group number 1)

Constructs	Indicators	skew	kurtosis
Agricultural Financing	AF1	-0.244	-0.795
	AF2	-0.421	-0.325
	AF3	-0.012	-0.904
	AF4	-0.143	-0.449
Market orientation	MO1	-0.432	-0.121
	MO2	-0.544	-0.085
	MO3	-0.298	-0.682
	MO4	-0.249	-0.44
	MO5	-0.132	-0.503
Agricultural innovation	AI5	-0.484	-0.425
	AI4	-0.52	-0.268
	AI3	-0.537	-0.319

	AI2	-0.499	0.195
	AI1	-0.717	0.477
ICT	ICT3	-0.289	-0.118
	ICT2	-0.194	0.212
	ICT1	-0.176	0.071
Agricultural Extension	AE1	-0.388	-0.422
	AE2	-0.582	-0.286
	AE3	-0.203	-0.581
	AE4	-0.172	-0.258

Goodness of Fit of Measurement Model

The measurement model’s properties were assessed by testing the convergent validity, reliability, and discriminant validity. The value of composite reliability (C.R.) for all factors see Table 4 below was higher than 0.6, so approving the reliability of the model [25]. Table 4 showed that the factor loadings of all items were larger than 0.5. Also, we checked the values of average variance extracted (AVE) for all constructs which were also higher than 0.5, approving the convergent validity of the model[26]. We evaluated the square root of AVE for each construct of the model (diagonal values)

in Table 5 which were higher than inner construct correlations (off-diagonal values), showing discriminant validity for the model Table 4 showed that the measurement model lights the condition for the reliability and validity of the constructs and discriminant validity. Professional thoughts demonstrated satisfactory validity in terms of instrument validity. Cronbach’s Alphas (α) test was used to assess the reliability of the constructed instrument, with a significance level of ($\alpha \geq 0.7$) as recommended in [27]. The purpose of the factor analysis test was to ensure that the degree of relevance of each item in the design was correct. First, the measurement model’s properties were evaluated by checking the convergent validity, reliability, and discriminant validity. To see if the measurement model matches the sample adequately, several goodness-of-fit indices are used. For the data results, the p-value of the Chi-square was 0.000 ($\chi^2 = 455.282$, $df = 182$). For a proper model fit, the p-value should be greater than 0.05, as a rule of thumb. In contrast, we discovered that the Chi-square is overly sensitive for the samples due to the sample size effect, implying that this chi-square test nearly rejects the model [28]. As a result, using the normed Chi-square (χ^2 / df) (Wheaton et al., 2014) is one way to resolve the issue of sample size impact. A normed Chi-square between 1 and 5 was reported by[29]. In this analysis, the samples’ value was $\chi^2 / df = 2.502$, indicating an acceptable match. Other indices such as the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), The Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed-Fit Index (NFI), and Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) were used to verify whether the model fit. The CFI and TLI values should be equal to or higher than 0.90, and the RMSEA should be less than 0.08, and the SRMR should be less than 0.08 [30], [31] All of the measurement model’s applicable fit indexes ($\chi^2 = 455.282$, $df = 182$, $p < 0.001$; $\chi^2 / df = 2.502$; CFI = 0.911; TLI = 0.897; RMSEA = 0.078; SRMR = 0.01615) were within the expected limits, demonstrating that the measurement model fulfilled all of the model fit requirements. Table 3, 4 below shows the structural equation model results.

Table 3 Validity and reliability of the measurement model

Construct	item	Factor loading	AVE	Cronbach's	CR
Market Orientation	MO1	0.743	0.508936	0.803	0.869
	MO2	0.788			
	MO3	0.753			
	MO4	0.594			
	MO5	0.669			
Agricultural financing	AF1	0.801	0.723522	0.809	0.928
	AF2	0.659			
	AF3	0.696			
	AF4	0.753			
Agricultural extension	AE1	0.827	0.625188	0.862	0.836
	AE2	0.825			
	AE3	0.722			
	AE4	0.785			
ICT	ICT1	0.878	0.811223	0.939	0.927
	ICT2	0.893			
	ICT3	0.930			
Agricultural Innovation	AI1	0.894	0.531429	0.898	0.818
	AI2	0.883			
	AI3	0.865			
	AI4	0.844			
	AI5	0.760			

Table 4 The hypothesis for different paths

Hypothesis	Path	Standardized regression	t-value	Significant	Hypothesis results
H1	Market orientation → ICT	0.36	5.3	P<0.05	Supported
H2	Agricultural Financing → ICT	0.42	6.1	P<0.05	Supported
H3	Agricultural Extension → ICT	0.25	4.0	P<0.05	Supported
H4	ICT → Agricultural Innovation	0.23	4.2	P<0.05	Supported

H5	Market Orientation → Agricultural innovation	0.28	3.4	P<0.05	Supported
H6	Agricultural Financing → Agricultural innovation	0.30	3.4	P<0.05	Supported
H7	Agricultural Extension → Agricultural innovation	0.09	068	P>.05	Unsupporte d

Fit indices: Chi-square/df = 2.502; GFI:0.851; AGFI:0.801; TLI:0.897; CFI:0.911; RMSEA:0.78;

H1 (MO) had a positive effect on (ICT) ($\beta = 0.36, p<0.05$) and H2 Agriculture financing (AF) was also significantly positive on (ICT). H3 Agricultural extension (AE) has a positive impact on (ICT) as well ($\beta = 0.42, p<0.05$), H4 as it was seen in the results ICT, has a positive effect on agricultural innovation (AI) ($\beta = 0.25, p<0.05$), H5 Market orientation (MO) is significantly positive AE) on Agricultural innovation (AI) ($\beta = 0.28, p<0.05$). H6 Agricultural financing (AF) as well, has a positive impact on Agricultural innovation (AI) ($\beta = 0.30, p<0.05$)
However, agricultural extension does not have any effect on agricultural innovation (AI) ($\beta = 0.09, p<0.05$) overall, the model fit. Based on the above results:

Correlation Matrix Divergent Validity

	AE	AI	MO	ICT	AF
AE	0.625				
AI	0.185	0.723			
MO	-0.378	-0.260	0.508		
ICT	-0.421	-0.277	0.397	0.811	
AF	0.355	0.122	-0.133	-0.361	0.531

Note: * Significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed); ** Significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

Discussion

This research looked at the impact of ICT on the innovation of tea farmers in Rwanda. The findings of this research reveal that ICT has a beneficial effect on agricultural finance and market orientation, which led to greater agricultural innovation, which may be explained by findings, which show that ICT can lead to agricultural innovation [7], [8]. The findings also show that ICT improves agricultural financing, market orientation, and agricultural extension. The mediator and the independent variable constructs have a pleasant relationship. That suggests that ICT, as a tool, has a positive impact not only in our daily lives but also on the farm. It positively influences market orientation, agricultural financing, and agricultural extension. According to the hypothesis, the independent variables generally influence agricultural innovation positively, but the agricultural extension has a smaller impact on innovation. The agricultural extension does not directly lead to innovation, which is explained by the fact that Rwandan farmers are already grouped in many farming cooperatives, and communication among them is already at a high level. This is not surprising because the art of communication and working together among tea farmers in Rwanda is not new, and

the local government is always involved in updating farmers' skills, introducing new varieties, and working hand in hand with the farmers [19].

To address modern challenges of innovation, they must be market-oriented and consider what the final consumer wants and needs. There is also a need to increase financing in agriculture, which is the primary employer in Rwanda, and tea is the primary subsector, so more investment is required. Another unexpected finding is that the relationship between ICT and independent variables is more fruitful than the relationship between ICT and dependent variables. That is explained by the fact that simply having an Internet connection on a mobile phone is insufficient to innovate if there is a lack of understanding of the final end consumer and other involved stakeholders are not equally involved in developing market-oriented products[32].

Conclusion

The economy of Rwanda and its farmers both benefit from innovation in the tea industry. Tea farming in Rwanda has a long history and is very vital to Rwanda's economy. The primary goal of this study is to highlight how crucial it is to use ICT to innovate Rwanda's tea-producing sector. This study investigates how ICT applications for market orientation, agricultural financing, and agricultural extension can lead to innovation in the tea-producing sector. Based on earlier literature searches on related problems, five study hypotheses have been created. A total of 250 residents of Rwanda's western provinces took part in the study and answered 22 questions. Finally, a full explanation and the material were gathered and presented. This study has several limitations because the data was gathered from the perspectives of farmers, wholesalers, distributors, and exporters. As inter-organizational solutions to uncertainty may be required, future research may be enhanced by involving consumers. Institutions and stakeholders must pay special attention to population growth and the dearth of resources needed to meet the population's expanding needs. According to prior talks, central government policies have a significant impact on the growth of the tea business. Innovations in the tea sector will also be ensured through the best use of political measures. Findings from the study may have significant additional advantages for regional and national growth, particularly in regard to tea farming, ICT advancements, and agricultural advances. Additionally, the results may encourage companies to invest in tea farming while working with farmers and other involved stakeholders to achieve a common goal, thereby advancing agricultural tea farming innovation. The nature of the data and the sample size employed are two examples of the study's limitations. The model does not take into account the factors that are commonly used to predict innovations, such as regulatory, economic, and knowledge supply factors. Therefore, an empirical reexamination of Tea's innovation determinant should take these elements into account. Investments in the tea industry should be improved, there is a need to Strengthen the government's macro-control in improving the tea farming industry in Rwanda

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper

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